

Identifying the Factors of Slums Development in Urban Areas of Qasimabad, Sindh Pakistan

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Abstract

The term slum is often used to describe hectic settlements with poor facilities and bad living conditions. The majority of city dwellers reside in slums, which are typically deprived of the most basic utilities. According to UN-HABITAT's definition of slum refers to a group of people who live in close residences in urban areas and who require enough living space, long-term housing, access to consumption of water, and a proper sanitation system. Slums developed in Pakistan, like many other third-world nations, are a result of rising urbanization, and the government's incapacity to provide rural migrants in urban centers with housing needs. Hyderabad is one of the fastest-growing cities in the State that has seen significant industrialization. Qasimabad sub-local, being the area most affected by the urbanization process in the Hyderabad region, as a result, 3508 agricultural land parcels were turned into a housing development. The aim of this research is to identify the factors and slum development in urban areas of Qasimabad through the data collection process, specific observation is made, and reports are reviewed. Secondary data is collected in the form of census reports, master plans, and various evaluations, used to examine the issues with slums. However, the results show that the primary cause of the overpopulation of slums and environmental degradation in urban areas is the declination of secondary cities.

Index Terms: Migrations, Push and Pull Factors, Rapid Urbanization in Pakistan, Slum Areas in Qasimabad, Unplanned Settlements.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant and pressing global challenges is overpopulation since it demands sufficient social and economic amenities [1]. Due to the way urban areas expand and become economically active, there needs to be enough space for residential, commercial, industrial, and educational purposes. This often could involve destroying valuable agricultural land that is surrounded by a city [2]. Further ensuring and managing social and economic comfort is a difficult problem that requires the cooperation of economists, lawmakers, policymakers, and scientists. The majority of the land degradation occurring worldwide is caused by industrial, agricultural, livestock, inadequate irrigation, deforestation, and wealthy urbanization [3].

A slum is a large urban informal community that is known for its insolvency and substandard housing. The industrial, agricultural, livestock, inadequate irrigation, deforestation, and urbanization of the rich are the primary causes of global land degradation [4]. In a similar line, the only source of food, clothes, fuel, and shelter that humans need is land [5]. According to UN-HABITAT's global assessment of slums, 924 million people, or 32% of the world's urban population, live in slums. Approximately 43% of city dwellers in the modern, expanding globe reside in slums [6].

In Pakistan, agriculture contributes to around 19.8% of the country's GDP, supports 42.3% of the population, directly and indirectly employs over 70% of the labor force, and

exports agricultural goods at a rate of about 45%. While the population of rural areas continues to decline, with a steady decline from 61.4% in 2014 to 60.1 % in 2019, the population of urban areas is increasing, from 38.5% in 2014 to 40.0% in 2019 [7].

With 40,000 persons per km², Hyderabad has the highest population density in the nation (see figure I). According to government figures, Hyderabad is one of the most densely inhabited areas in the Nation with a 3.6% growth rate in population (Demographic, 2015). Additional population growth trends are also available. Conflicts over food and land use may develop in the future if agricultural land is converted to urban centers because most cities are encroaching on rural territory [8].

Push and pull factors play crucial roles in shaping migration patterns [9] and due to rising urbanization and the government's incapacity to provide rural migrants in metropolitan centers with essential living accommodations. Pakistan has slums like many other third-world nations [10]. Hyderabad is one of the fastest-growing cities in the nation, has seen tremendous industrialization, with Qasimabad covering more than 49,800-acre land including more than 250 housing developments as well as 70 'Katchi Abadis', or impromptu communities [11].

The most terrible environmental and active conditions are consumed by these communities, which are shown by a lack of water supply, filthy conditions of natural sanitation, crowded and weathered housing, risky location, and

weakening of residence, as well as difficult economic and social conditions [12].

Figure I: Area and Population Density of Pakistan's Largest Cities (Source: Peerzado, 2019)

II. STUDY AREA

One of the Hyderabad's towns and talukas that are expanding quickly is Qasimabad (see figure II). The vast bulk of the inhabitants are transplants from rural areas. The upgrade of the seepage system remains behind the expanding population, which is estimated to be over 450,000. Only water pumps may be utilized in the region to remove wastewater because Qasimabad lacks a drainage

system or rainfall drains. In their location, muck and filth are overflowing the water channel (see figure III) [13]. Qasimabad Taluka is chosen as a case study. It is in the western portion of Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan. As a case study, it examines how different commuters observe current trends in urban land use planning. It is situated at coordinates 25.24 °N latitude, and 68.20 °E longitude. The site has a total size of around 49,800 acres, which includes both built and undeveloped land. Additionally, it is administratively separated into four Union Councils, with Qasimabad serving as its administrative center [14]. The waterway is more than eight km long and is known as the 'Wadhu Wah' distributary. From the 'Phuleli Canal', it emerges. However, the three-kilometer section that goes through Qasimabad is clogged with muck. Two main roadways run transverse over densely inhabited private colonies and loft buildings on each side of the distributary. However the residents of all of these so-called wealthy regions in Qasimabad experience several issues as a result of the drainage system and rain [15]. The Qasimabad municipal officials have been dumping heavy garbage on a plot of land. In an eight to ten-acre tract of land that is bounded by the sports complex which is now functioning in the community for trash dumping, i.e., Qasimabad Sports Complex, huge volumes of waste are deposited and devoured every day (see figure IV). There are a lot of people who live in the states and a lot of residences in the Katchi Abadis [16].

Figure II: Map of the Hyderabad Region (The Study Area) (Source: Abbasi, et.al. 2019)

Figure III: Water Channel (Wadhu Wah) Qasimabad, Hyderabad Sindh

Figure IV: Huge Garbage in the Sports Complex in Qasimabad

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to UN-HABITAT (2012), during the past 50 years, Asia has seen huge demographic changes, one of which is the transfer of people from rural regions, which is why the percentage of people living in urban areas is rapidly rising [17]. Only 17% of Asia's total population—232 million people—lived in cities in 1950, making up just 232 million people. Urban populations increased to 1.6 billion in 2005, accounting for 40% of Asia's overall population. By 2025, the United Nations projects that more than 50% of Asia's population will reside in cities, with that number rising to 54.5% by 2030 [18]. There are three factors, that contribute to this significant rise in the urban population: Natural population growth, rural-to-urban migration, and by reclassifying of rural areas as urban areas defined by Opondo and Makindi in 2023. It was discovered that while the number of urban inhabitants is growing, 37% of the world's population still resides in slums as a result of widespread rural-urban movement and emigration from smaller to larger cities [19]. Residents of slums have minimal access to public services like healthcare and education. One-third of the population of Dhaka lives in slums, where a lack of access to basic amenities, inadequate water supply, and inadequate waste disposal contribute to a variety of health issues [20]. According to a 2012 United Nations estimate, 533 million people, or 42% of all metropolitan Asians, live in slums. The majority of these individuals are regular, hardworking people who cannot afford adequate housing [21]. According to Potsiou and Pugh, 30% of the urban population in developing nations lives in slums or other informal settlements. In Sub-Saharan Africa, slums make up around 90% of all new urban settlements, and they are frequently constructed in high-risk, hazardous areas that might be affected by climate change [22]. According to

Hussain in 2019 Katchi Abadis emerged on the periphery of major cities or next to high-income residential areas for economic reasons [23]. According to a report by UNHSP and UNESCAP (2008), informal settlements in Asian cities might be of any size or shape, but they always share a highly dynamic reaction to the complete absence of alternatives. The urban migrants from the countryside carried their felt-lined tents with them to the Mongolian capital. 55% of people in Mumbai, India, live in slums, and many of them cannot afford to own homes there [24]. 35000 households in Manila, the Philippines, collect recyclable rubbish for a living yet still have to live in substandard housing. Slums that are located alongside railway tracks and waterways are where Thailand's urban poor are compelled to dwell [25].

A. Causes of Slum Conditions

In the past 15 years, slums have expanded at an unprecedented rate. Slums are becoming a prominent and distinctive kind of habitation in many cities in the developing world [26]. Through the greatest annual slum and urban growth rates (4.53% and 4.58%, respectively) essentially similar, urbanization has practically become synonymous with slum growth. The 2009 World Progress Report regards slum growth as an unavoidable "growing pain" of economic progress, in contrast to past approaches regarding slums that characterized them as unlawful settlements to be removed [27].

Not another miracle of the slum. These represent a portion of the historical background of the best urban districts, notably during the early, protracted periods of growth and industrialization when the population was obnoxious. In metropolitan regions, where competition for land and wages is fierce, slums are frequently the main kind of habitation that is affordable and near to the poor [28]. Slums are created for two main reasons: population increase and poor governance.

B. Growth in Population

Nations from all over, more and more people move from rural to urban regions and as population growth as usual continues, the world is fast being urbanised. The majority of the world's population currently lives in urban areas. More than 90% of this town's growth is being driven by the construction industry [29].

Some individuals are pushed away from their home countries due to events like natural disasters or long-term ecological changes. Others are pulled to a new location by better employment, educational, or healthcare opportunities, as well as freedom from restrictive social or cultural norms [30]. The agricultural industry, which is heavily reliant on the weather, employs the majority of people in rural regions. Additionally, rural land is scarce, its fertility is occasionally poor or deteriorating, land holdings are modest, agricultural loans are substantial, and a significant portion of households no longer own any property. As a result, rural earnings are often low [31]. The number of work prospects in metropolitan regions is significantly higher than in rural ones. In addition, cities might provide more opportunities for upward social mobility since metropolitan cultures are frequently less restricted than those in rural areas [32]. The majority of

migrants consciously choose to remain in or leave rural regions. Rural inhabitants are far more aware of the benefits and drawbacks of urban living because of improved transit, communications, and connections with previous migrants, particularly in terms of employment and housing [33]. Rural households frequently migrate to cities as a means of survival. Rural homes can occasionally be divided into a number of groupings that are spread out. Rural villages, small towns, and major cities could expand their income sources and reduce their exposure to economic crises [34].

Table I shows the census report by the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS) where millions of people were across Pakistan with a growth rate of 2.55 % in 2023.

Table I: Population of Pakistan with Growth Rate

Admin Unit	Population (mill)			Annual Growth Rate %		
	1998	2017	2023	1998	2017	2023
KPK	20.92	35.50	40.85	2.72	2.82	2.38
Punjab	73.62	109.98	127.68	2.64	2.13	2.53
Sindh	30.44	47.85	55.69	2.80	2.41	2.57
Baluchistan	6.57	12.34	14.89	2.47	3.37	3.20
Islamabad	0.81	2.01	2.36	5.19	4.91	2.81
Pakistan	132.35	207.68	241.49	2.69	2.40	2.55

C. Governance Growth

Poor administration is another reason slums exist. Governments routinely disregard the rights of the urban poor and fail to integrate them into urban areas, which leads to the development of slums [35-36].

Another crucial factor is how a government feels about urbanization. Some governments see urbanization negatively. They think that by offering urban amenities to the underprivileged, urbanization would be attracted, leading to the expansion of slums [37]. The issue with this

perspective is that few people visit cities for utilities like water; instead, they come in search of employment. In other situations, governments handle urbanization more passively. They either lack the planning tools necessary to address the current fast urbanization, or those that are available are insufficiently responsive to the reality on the ground [38].

D. Housing Challenges and Issues in Pakistan's Urban Areas

Sprawl is expanding exponentially in emerging nations, and it is currently considered the modern trend of the current globalized sphere. This tendency is advancing extremely quickly thanks to daily revolutionary technologies [39]. People are being encouraged to travel and leave their houses as a result of this new modernizing practice. One is interested in learning how this significant development is influencing our world since everything has both good and bad effects. The continent where one may see the fastest rate of urbanization is Asia, in particular [40].

Due to the fact that no country can tolerate a pause in the growth of economic advancement, urbanization cannot be completed. If the housing problem isn't addressed properly and on time, it will only get worse [41]. The dream of a reasonable or proper housing settlement for the inner-city poor can become a reality if the present settlements of the poor are taken care of with real arranging and the board and appropriate use of arranging arrangements under the supervision of worthy administration [42]. According to the following data, Pakistan's city population has increased fast between 1950 and 2000 and is expected to continue to grow between 2000 and 2050 [43]. See figure V for ease of understanding.

Figure V: Urbanization's Connections to Demographic and Urban Development (Source: F. Mazhar, 2009)

IV. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Qasimabad region was selected as the study area for this research. Hyderabad is the second largest city of Sindh Province which ranked seventh in the overall city ranking of Pakistan. As shown in figure VI, the city is administratively divided into four Talukas, namely, Hyderabad City, Qasimabad, Latifabad, and Hyderabad Rural.

The primary goals of this research are to analyze the current physical environment, design sites, analyze social and economic issues, analyze land use activities, and offer workable methods to prevent the emergence of slums. In order to obtain data for this research, active document inspection and individual opinion were necessary. The secondary data from census reports, grasp formats, and other reports were used to thoroughly analyze the growth patterns of the study area in Qasimabad, Hyderabad. The researcher also traveled to the case study locations to observe the standard of living there.

Figure VI: Administrative Area Distribution - Hyderabad District (Source: S. Memon et.al (2023))

Table II demonstrates the 3.6 (360%) growth rates in population for the Hyderabad district between 1951 and 2017. With a 34.1 (3410%) rise rate (GOP, 2017), Qasimabad.

Table II: Population of Hyderabad During Six Censuses (2016, 2017 for the GOP)

Area Name	Population						Growth Rate %
	1951	1961	1972	1981	1988	1998	
Hyderabad District(overall)	625,848	93199	1,623,864	2,022,305	2,834,451	2,908,147m	3.6
Hyderabad City Sub-District	242,651	436,171	630,624	394,853	525,299	538,957	1.2
Qasimabad Sub-District	3370	5225	9448	32043	115,374	118,374	34.1
Latifabad Sub-District	3780	7968	14,517	366,799	563,761	578419	152
Hyderabad Rural Sub-District	69,431	87,636	159,471	211,765	290,432	197,983	3.3

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Qasimabad district in Hyderabad Development Authority (HDA) is one of the most significant districts in terms of agricultural land conversion with 3508 acres of land converted. The results of the study show that Hyderabad is expanding over time, with Qasimabad district serving as the key economic hub for 3508 acres of priceless agricultural land during the past ten years (see figure VII).

Figure VII: Change in Acres of Agricultural Land during the Last Ten Years

According to Table III, Qasimabad leads the way in property transformation with an average rate of 97%, followed by Hyderabad City with 70%, Latifabad with 69%, and rural Hyderabad with 35%. While 70% of agricultural property was exchanged and altered in urban areas. People exchanged their non-industrialized property for cash, for communal, commercial, and agricultural purposes. People relocate to adjacent areas where land costs are affordable for middle-class residents when prices rise but are still close to urban areas but outside of the urban boundaries.

Table III: Sub-Emergence of Agricultural Lands into Urbanization

Particulars	Agriculture Land Sold / Acre Total	Sold
Hyderabad City Sub-District	30	21
Qasimabad Sub-District	32	31
Latifabad Sub-District	16	11
Hyderabad rural Sub-District	26	9
Overall Hyderabad District	104	72

Figure VIII, below shows unplanned neighborhoods, sometimes known as slums, shantytowns, or informal settlements, in the Qasimabad districts. These lands are part of rural areas that were once utilized for agriculture, but with suburbanization, they are now used for things like schools, markets, housing settlements, and transportation. The lack of essential infrastructure and services in these

communities might result in poor living circumstances for the locals. Due to their location and inadequate infrastructure, these communities are especially at risk of disasters like landslides and floods.

Figure VIII: Unplanned Settlements in Qasimabad District

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The urban area of Qasimabad has expanded massively in the previous several years. People are migrating to Qasimabad from various regions of interior Sindh for a variety of reasons, including employment, education, health, and environmental circumstances. The surrounding rural poor moved to cities in search of work and industrial expansion, which turned the city into a hub of economic activity and led to the development of agricultural land's infrastructure as a whole. Due to the acceleration of urbanization, there has been an increase in the growth of slums and unregulated land conversion around the periphery of cities, eventually expanding urban built-up beyond municipal jurisdiction. Several housing projects have been introduced along an important highway that connects to Qasimabad. It has led to the conversion of a significant amount of agricultural land into urban areas. After investigation, it shows that 3508 acres of priceless agricultural land in Qasimabad have been transformed into urban areas. The unplanned and unregulated urban expansion of Qasimabad has led to disorganized buildings along the main routes. Everyone with an interest should take note of this concerning scenario and do their part to improve the area's growth. For intelligent and sustainable land use in the city, strict land conversion laws and locally needed, need-based land use planning are necessary.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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